

doi:10.5281/zenodo.19111002

Career Fair Guidance Strategies for Increasing Students' Choice of Vocational and Technical Education Subjects in Secondary Schools in Delta State

Ofulue, Justina I.; Prof. Christian A. Oduma & Dr. Friday Ogbaga

¹Department of Office Technology and Management
Delta State Polytechnic Ogwushi-Uku, Delta State, Nigeria

^{2,3}Department of Business Education,
Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to identify the Career fair guidance strategies for increasing students' choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools in Delta State. One specific purposes, research questions and hypothesis guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The population of the study comprised of 3,585 (1,594 males and 1991 females) teachers of Vocational and Technical Education subjects from 488 public secondary schools in the 11 Education Zones in Delta State. Sample size of 717 teachers of Vocational and Technical Education subjects was used for the study. A structured questionnaire containing 10 items entitled: Career Guidance Strategies for Increasing Students' Choice of Vocational and Technical Education Subjects in Secondary Schools Questionnaire (CGSQ) was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts and tested for reliability using Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient. The overall reliability coefficient obtained was 0.97. Seven hundred and seventeen copies of the questionnaire were administered with the help of three research assistants, and 542 were retrieved from the respondents. Data collected were analyzed using mean to answer the research questions, and t-test statistic was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that career fair guidance strategies included: setting up displays that provide information about the different career paths in vocational and technical education; inviting professionals from vocational and technical industries to participate in the career fair; organizing hands-on activities that promotes practical aspects of VTE careers; arranging for guest speakers from vocational and technical backgrounds to make presentations during the career fair; conducting panel discussions with expert professionals from vocational and technical fields among others. The hypothesis tested showed that gender teachers of vocational and technical education subjects did not show significant differences in their mean responses on career information guidance strategies for increasing students' choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools in Delta State. The implication of the findings is that lack of career guidance in secondary schools may perpetuate students' low interest and enrollment in VTE subjects, leading to a shortage of skilled workers in various industries which may exacerbate the skills gap in various industries, making it challenging for employers to find qualified candidates. It was recommended that school administrators/Principal should organize career fairs that bring together industry professionals, employers, and students to promote vocational and technical education subjects and career opportunities.

Keywords: Career Guidance, Strategies, Students', Choice, Vocational and Technical Education

INTRODUCTION

There is an urgent need for Nigeria's focus to be towards self-sufficient and sustainable means of subsistence that VTE provides. However, it appears that secondary schools in Nigeria have failed to guide students to make effective career choices that would improve their capacity for self-employment amidst the current economic downturn being faced in Nigeria. The perception of Vocational and Technical education (VTE) in Nigeria is influenced by societal attitudes and educators perspectives. As Okoye and Arimonu (2016) suggest, there is a prevailing notion in Nigerian society that VTE subjects are suitable for academically weak students who may not pursue higher education. This perception is compounded by the fact that teachers responsible for delivering VTE programme often lack adequate knowledge about the relevance and importance of these subjects. (Adewale, Aderonmu, Fulani, Babalola and Awoyera, 2018). This appears to result in poor students' interest in VTE subjects in secondary schools in Delta State. It is therefore pertinent that career guidance strategies are adopted so as to improve students' interest in VTE.

Career guidance strategies refer to the approaches, methods, and techniques used to support individuals in making informed decisions about their career paths. These strategies aim to help individuals explore their interests, skills, and values; identify career options; and develop plans to achieve their career goals (Partha, 2020). Career guidance strategies are essential in the secondary school system for addressing students' physical, social, emotional, vocational, and academic issues in order to improve their wellness, academic performance, and career choice making. This may have prompted Eremie and Jackson (2019) to argue that every teacher should be guidance focused in the process of carrying out his or her duties with the goal of creating an influence in the lives of the students. Partha (2020) asserted that career guidance strategy is a plan for moving our lives in the right direction. Nwachi and Ndimele (2021) stated that the career guidance strategies available in schools and communities in general include information services, testing services, placement services, appraisal services, orientation services, evaluation services, referral services, research services, follow-up services, consultation, co-ordination, collaboration, instruction, and institutional support. Partha (2020) opined that academic information, career information, group guidance, counseling, orientation, and assessment are part of the career guidance strategies.

Vocational and Technical Education is any form of education that strives to improve students' abilities and potential so they can do tasks or work in a certain vocation effectively (Okoro in Ozoemena, 2013). VTE can be delivered in a variety of ways: It may be formal or informal, structured or unstructured and it may be institutionalized or community-based. The main goal of vocational and technical education subjects is to prepare students for the workforce. VTE, according to Winer in Igbozurike, Peter and Usman (2018), strives to broaden the learner's skills, talents, knowledge, and awareness of work etiquette and attitude needed to thrive in a specific line of work or occupation. According to Alam (2015), VTE is not only highly beneficial because it gives people the technical, entrepreneurial, and vocational skills they need for a competitive edge, but it also expands their awareness of workplace circumstances, obligations, social and civic duties. According to this definition, TVE can also be described as a type of education that fosters the development of learners' technical and vocational skills, expertise, dexterity, talents, and attitudes through any combination of formal or informal education, on-the-job training, or off-the-job training.

Vocational and technical education provides students with a structured programme of learning experiences that includes career exploration, basic academic and life skills support, achievement of high academic standards, leadership development, industry-specific job preparation, and advanced and continuing education. Okoye and Okwelle (2013) viewed VTE as an education system expected to produce a competent workforce that can compete and excel in a rapidly changing environment and improve a country's economy. Vocational and technical education is concerned with the development of skills, competences, and knowledge for the working world (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization International Centre for TVET (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2019). It includes formal, informal, and non-formal education. It influences people's attitudes and develops abilities and knowledge from fundamental to advanced levels. The importance of VTE cannot be overstated, particularly in the light of the fact that many secondary school dropouts and even university graduates often lack essential

occupational and life skills (Eze and Okorafor, 2012). According to Igbozuruike, Ebinu and Onu (2017), continued neglect of VTE is the cause of this situation. Although it has become abundantly evident that lack of practical skills among school dropouts is the primary cause of Nigeria's growing unemployment rate. It is stated that less than one percent of secondary education in Nigeria is designed to promote VTE and skills development (Igbozuruike, 2018). As there is scarcely any discernible leadership or direction for revitalizing VTE, the terrible situation has not improved and is really becoming worse.

Career fairs for secondary school students are events that are held to allow individuals to explore numerous career alternatives and receive useful insights into various professions. Representatives from many companies, educational institutions, and organizations generally attend these fairs to connect with students and provide information about career paths, job possibilities, and educational needs. Buzzetta and Eskin (n.d.) defined a career fair as an event that allows students and companies to interact, build professional contacts, and discuss prospective job and/or internship prospects. Career Fair, also mentioned as a job fair or career expo, is a fair or exposition for recruiters to meet with prospective job seekers. Job seekers attend these to make a good impression by getting advantage of speaking face-to-face with recruiters and submitting resumes. For human resource specialists and job-recruiters, career fairs are one of the instruments that allow for effective communication with prospective candidates. It also serves as an opening to attract the finest talent (Silkes, 2010) and to also increase the brand awareness and be the employer of the potential talent (Gordon, 2014). The educational institutions perceive the career fair as a showcase of its brightest talents to reputable firms.

Career fair is an important career guidance strategy for secondary school students (Mathe and Hapazari, 2018). There is a significant demand for career counseling and innovative programmes for students (Buzzeo and Cifci, 2017). Career fairs offer a venue for professional growth, a chance for networking, and a means to look for an internship or employment. Mathe and Hapazari (2018) stated that there are several advantages of visiting a career fair, regardless of your major, academic year, or future objectives. They include: increase the likelihood that students will be invited to an employment interview; enlarge your network of connections; look into jobs, careers, and fields of study that are compatible with your background and major; open openings, and get wise job-search guidance from knowledgeable corporate recruiters. These career fairs are significant because they allow students to take advantage of the opportunity to learn about career paths, education and training, and employment prospects (Walter, 2012). Students must understand why they are attending careers and training fair or careers market in order to obtain value from it (Partha, 2020). They must also understand what information they will be able to access at the fair (Budzanowska-drzewiecka and Proszowska, 2015). According to Nwachi and Ndimele (2021), career orientation strategy is another career guidance strategy that could be used in secondary schools.

Career fairs are an important strategy for career guidance among secondary school students (Mathe and Hapazari, 2018). There is a growing demand for career counseling and innovative programmes tailored to students' needs (Buzzeo and Cifci, 2017). Career fairs provide valuable opportunities for professional growth, networking, and exploration of internships and employment prospects. Hanson, Hoole and Cox (2017) noted that alumni activities, business games and career fairs may also be utilized to provide students with career guidance information. Mathe and Hapazari (2018) stated that there are several advantages of visiting a career fair, regardless of your major, academic year, or future objectives. They included: increase the likelihood that students will be invited to an employment interview; enlarge your network of connections; look into jobs, careers, and fields of study that are compatible with your background and major; study up on employers, open vacancies and get wise job-search guidance from knowledgeable corporate recruiters. According to Mathe and Hapazari (2018), visiting a career fair offers several advantages regardless of one's major, academic year, or future objectives. These include increasing the likelihood of being invited for job interviews, expanding professional networks, exploring career paths and fields of study that align with one's background and major, learning about employers and job openings, and receiving valuable job search guidance from experienced corporate recruiters. Career fairs are significant as they allow students to gain insights into various career paths, education and

training requirements, and employment prospects (Walter, 2012). To fully benefit from attending career fairs, students should understand their purpose for attending and what kind of information they can expect to access (Budzanowska-drzewiecka and Proszowska, 2015).

Career fairs play a crucial role in enhancing students' interest in vocational and technical education programmes. These events provide a platform for students to explore various vocational and technical career options, interact with industry professionals, and gain valuable insights into the benefits and opportunities offered by these educational pathways (Nwachi and Ndimele, 2021). By participating in career fairs, students can engage in hands-on activities, demonstrations, and informational sessions related to vocational and technical fields. They can interact with professionals from different industries, ask questions, and learn about the practical aspects of these careers. This exposure helps students develop a better understanding of the skills and knowledge required in vocational and technical fields, as well as the potential career prospects and growth opportunities available. Career fairs also provide students with the opportunity to witness the real-world applications of vocational and technical education. They can observe live demonstrations, exhibitions, and presentations showcasing the innovative projects and achievements of students in these programmes (Mathe and Hapazari, 2018). This firsthand experience can ignite their interest, inspire creativity, and motivate them to pursue vocational and technical education pathways. Furthermore, career fairs often feature discussions and panel sessions where students can interact with alumni and professionals who have successfully pursued vocational and technical careers. These interactions allow students to gain valuable insights, advice, and mentorship, which can further stimulate their interest in vocational and technical education.

Statement of the Problem

The Nigerian education system is grappling with a pressing issue: the dwindling interest of students in Vocational and Technical Education (VTE) subjects in secondary schools. Despite the abundance of career opportunities and benefits associated with VTE, many students are deterred from pursuing these subjects, opting instead for more traditional academic pathways. For instance, a recent study by the National Bureau of Statistics (2020) revealed that only 15% of secondary school students in Nigeria choose VTE subjects, citing lack of awareness and perceived low job prospects as major factors. This trend has significant implications for Nigeria's economic development, as VTE is crucial for equipping students with the practical skills and competencies required to drive industrial growth and innovation. Career fairs have been identified as a potential solution to address this challenge, offering a unique platform for students to explore various career options, interact with industry professionals, and gain insights into the world of work. However, the effectiveness of career fairs in influencing students' subject choices depends on the guidance strategies employed. The Nigerian government has made efforts to promote VTE through initiatives such as the Technical Education and Vocational Training (TEVT) programme and the National Skills Qualification Framework (NSQF). Despite these efforts, VTE remains stigmatized, with many students and parents viewing it as a fallback option for those who cannot cope with academic rigour. Against this backdrop, effective career fair guidance is crucial for demystifying VTE, highlighting its relevance, and inspiring students to consider VTE subjects. The problem of this study is to identify the career fair guidance strategies for increasing VTE subjects in secondary schools in Delta State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to identify the career fair guidance strategies for increasing students' choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools in Delta State. Specifically, the study sought to identify:

the career fair guidance strategies for increasing students' choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools in Delta State.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

What are the career fair guidance strategies for increasing students' choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools in Delta State?

Hypothesis

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of teachers in rural and urban secondary schools on career fair guidance strategies for increasing students’ choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools in Delta State.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The study was conducted in Delta State, located in the South-South region of Nigeria. The population of the study comprised of 3,585 (1,594 males and 1991 females) teachers of Vocational and Technical Education subjects from 488 public secondary schools in the 11 Education Zones in Delta State. Sample size of 717 teachers of Vocational and Technical Education subjects was used for the study. A structured questionnaire containing 50 items entitled: Career Fairs Guidance Strategies for Increasing Students’ Choice of Vocational and Technical Education Subjects in Secondary Schools Questionnaire (CGSQ) was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts and tested for reliability using Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient. The overall reliability coefficient obtained was 0.87. Seven hundred and seventeen copies of the questionnaire were administered with the help of five research assistants, and 542 were retrieved from the respondents. Data collected were analysed using mean to answer the research questions, and t-test statistic was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. A null hypothesis was rejected where the p-value was less than or equal to the 0.05 level of significance. The decision is to accept when P-value is greater than 0.05 and reject when the P-value is less than or equal to 0.05

RESULTS

Research Question One: *What are the career fair guidance strategies for increasing students’ choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools in Delta State?*

The data providing answers to the above research question are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Career Fair Guidance Strategies for Increasing Students’ Choice of Vocational and Technical Education Subjects in Secondary Schools

S/N	Items on Career fair Guidance Strategies	N	Mean	Std.	Remarks
1.	Setting up displays that provide information about the different career paths in vocational and technical education.	542	3.30	.70	S
2.	Inviting professionals from vocational and technical industries to participate in the career fair	542	3.40	.60	S
3.	Organizing hands-on activities that promotes practical aspects of VTE careers	542	3.36	.54	S
4.	Arranging for guest speakers from vocational and technical backgrounds to make presentations during the career fair	542	3.30	.63	S
5.	Conducting panel discussions with expert professionals from vocational and technical fields	542	3.26	.72	S
6.	Offering individualized career counseling sessions during the career fair	542	3.35	.65	S
7.	Inviting former students of vocational and technical education to share their experiences and achievements with students	542	3.36	.61	S
8.	Organizing workshops for parents and guardians on career opportunities associated with vocational and technical education	542	3.33	.63	S
9.	Availing students the opportunities to showcase their vocational and technical projects during the career fair.	542	3.20	.77	S
10.	Partnering with vocational and technical colleges or institutes to provide information on further education opportunities based on students' skills.	542	3.28	.66	S

Note: S= Strategies

Table 1 shows that all the strategies have mean scores ranging from 3.20 to 3.40. This implies that the career fair guidance strategies include: setting up displays that provide information about the different career paths in vocational and technical education; inviting professionals from vocational and technical industries to participate in the career fair; organizing hands-on activities that promotes practical aspects of VTE careers; arranging for guest speakers from vocational and technical backgrounds to make presentations during the career fair; conducting panel discussions with expert professionals from vocational and technical fields and so on.

Research Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of teachers in rural and urban secondary schools on career fair guidance strategies for increasing students' choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools

The t-test analysis of data collected to test the null hypothesis two is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: t-test Analysis on the Career Fair Guidance Strategies for Increasing Students' Choice of Vocational and Technical Education Subjects in Secondary School Based on Location

S/N	Location	N	Mean	Std	Df	t-cal	Alpha	P-Value	Decision
1	Urban	253	3.38	.73	540	2.407	0.05	.016	Significant
	Rural	289	3.23	.66					
2	Urban	253	3.42	.61	540	.983	0.05	.415	Not Significant
	Rural	289	3.37	.59					
3	Urban	253	3.28	.50	540	3.047	0.05	.000	Significant
	Rural	289	3.43	.56					
4	Urban	253	3.34	.58	540	1.178	0.05	.149	Not Significance
	Rural	289	3.27	.67					
5	Urban	253	3.23	.76	540	-.957	0.05	.538	Not Significant
	Rural	289	3.29	.69					
6	Urban	253	3.40	.64	540	1.592	0.05	.344	Not Significant
	Rural	289	3.31	.65					
7	Urban	253	3.43	.61	540	2.484	0.05	.131	Not Significant
	Rural	289	3.29	.61					
8	Urban	253	3.37	.58	540	1.448	0.05	.112	Not Significant
	Rural	289	3.29	.66					
9	Urban	253	3.20	.82	540	.239	0.05	.169	Not Significant
	Rural	289	3.21	.73					
10	Urban	253	3.27	.63	540	.207	0.05	.087	Not Significant
	Rural	289	3.28	.68					

The result of the t-test analyses in Table 2 indicates that most of the strategies have their P- values ranging from .087 to 0.415 which are greater than 0.05 indicating there is no significant difference in the mean responses of teachers in rural and urban secondary schools on career fair guidance strategies for increasing students' choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools in Delta State. While two strategies Setting up displays that provide information about the different career paths in vocational and technical education and organizing hands-on activities that promotes practical aspects of VTE careers only have P-value of less than 0.05 indicating a significant difference in response between urban and rural secondary school teachers.

DISCUSSION

The findings of the study showed that the respondents indicated that the career fair guidance strategies included: setting up displays that provide information about the different career paths in vocational and technical education; inviting professionals from vocational and technical industries to participate in the career fair; organizing hands-on activities that promotes practical aspects of VTE careers; arranging for guest speakers from vocational and technical backgrounds to make presentations during the career fair; conducting panel discussions with expert professionals from vocational and technical fields and offering

individualized career counseling sessions during the career fair. Others are: inviting former students of vocational and technical education to share their experiences and achievements with students; organizing workshops for parents and guardians on career opportunities associated with vocational and technical education; availing students the opportunities to showcase their vocational and technical projects during the career fair and partnering with vocational and technical colleges or institutes to provide information on further education opportunities based on students' skills.

The researcher is of the view that the result is so because career fairs play a crucial role in enhancing students' interest in vocational and technical education programmes. These events provide a platform for students to explore various vocational and technical career options, interact with industry professionals, and gain valuable insights into the benefits and opportunities offered by these educational pathways.

The findings of the study are in line with that of Hanson, Hoole and Cox (2017) who noted that alumni activities, business games and career fairs may also be utilized to provide students with career guidance information. The findings agreed with that of Mathe and Hapazari (2018) who stated that there are several advantages of visiting a career fair, regardless of your major, academic year, or future objectives. They included: increase the likelihood that students will be invited to an employment interview; enlarge your network of connections; look into jobs, careers, and fields of study that are compatible with your background and major; study up on employers, open vacancies and get wise job-search guidance from knowledgeable corporate recruiters. The findings also agree with the study of Walter (2012) who reported that career fairs are significant because they allow students to take advantage of the opportunity to learn about career paths, education and training, and employment prospects. In line with the findings, Partha (2020) also stated that students must understand why they are attending career and training fairs or career market in order to obtain value from it. By participating in career fairs, students can engage in hands-on activities, demonstrations, and informational sessions related to vocational and technical fields. They can interact with professionals from different industries, ask questions, and learn about the practical aspects of these careers. This exposure helps students develop a better understanding of the skills and knowledge required in vocational and technical fields, as well as the potential career prospects and growth opportunities available. The findings of this study are in line with Mathe and Hapazari, (2018) who posited that career fairs also provide students with the opportunity to witness the real-world applications of vocational and technical education. They can observe live demonstrations, exhibitions, and presentations showcasing the innovative projects and achievements of students in these programmes.

The findings of the study corroborate the findings of Mathe and Hapazari (2018) who noted that career fairs provide valuable opportunities for professional growth, networking, and exploration of internships and employment prospects. According to Mathe and Hapazari, visiting a career fair offers several advantages regardless of one's major, academic year or future objectives. These included increasing the likelihood of being invited for job interviews, expanding professional networks, exploring career paths and fields of study that align with one's background and major, learning about employers and job openings and receiving valuable job search guidance from experienced corporate recruiters. In agreement, Walter (2012) noted that Career fairs are significant as they allow students to gain insights into various career paths, education and training requirements, and employment prospects.

Further analysis revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of teachers in rural and urban secondary schools on all the career fair guidance strategies except setting up displays that provide information about the different career paths in vocational and technical education and organizing hands on activities that promotes practical aspects of VTE careers. The findings are in agreement with Boudreaux and Nikolaev (2019) who noted that schools, whether urban or rural, can benefit from career conventions similar to trade fairs, work experience programs, on-the-job training, alumni interactions, and parent conferences to guide students in making informed decisions about their future careers. The findings agree with Nugent, Barker, Welch, Grandgenett, Wu and Nelson (2015) who opine that schools located in rural or economically disadvantaged areas may have limited access to industry partners, career professionals, and resources that could provide students with exposure to various vocational and technical education pathways. In contrast, schools located in urban or more affluent areas may have better access

to such resources, which could facilitate more effective career fair guidance strategies. The findings agree with Byars-Winston, Estrada, Howard, Davis, and Zalapa (2010) who examined the influence of school location on career development interventions, to include career fairs. They found that interventions tailored to the specific needs and contexts of rural and urban schools were more effective in promoting students' interest in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) fields, which often overlap with vocational and technical education subjects. The findings agree with Nugent et al. (2015) who conducted a study on the effectiveness of career fairs in promoting STEM career interests among high school students in rural and urban settings. Their findings suggested that career fairs were more successful in urban settings where students had greater exposure to STEM professionals and resources.

CONCLUSION

The findings of the study revealed that career fair guidance strategies included: setting up displays that provide information about the different career paths in vocational and technical education; inviting professionals from vocational and technical industries to participate in the career fair; organizing hands-on activities that promotes practical aspects of VTE careers; arranging for guest speakers from vocational and technical backgrounds to make presentations during the career fair; conducting panel discussions with expert professionals from vocational and technical fields among others. The study also concluded that location of teachers of vocational and technical education subjects did not differ in their mean ratings on career fair guidance strategies for increasing students' choice of vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools in Delta State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that:

1. School administrators/Principal should organize career fairs that bring together industry professionals, employers, and students to promote vocational and technical education subjects and career opportunities.
2. School administrators/Principal should invite industry partners to participate in career fairs and provide students with information about vocational and technical education subjects in secondary schools in Delta State.
3. Federal and State government should develop more policies to support the integration of career fair guidance in secondary schools, including funding for career guidance programmes in secondary schools in Delta State.

REFERENCES

- Adewale, C. Aderonmu, F. Fulani, G., Babalola, B., and Awoyera, D. (2018). *Exploring gender differences in entrepreneurship: how the regulatory environment mitigates differences in early-stage growth aspirations*. In *High-growth Women's Entrepreneurship*. Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781788118712.00012>
- Alam, J. (2015). Preparing for a career fair. Retrieved from <https://career.fsu.edu/sites/g/files/imported/storage/original/application/1ad1d4dc79aa076c74409d97c046deaf.pdf>.
- Budzanowska-drzewiecka, M. and Proszowska, A. (2015). Attractiveness of job fairs for students as a platform for searching and exchange of information. *Jagiellonian Journal of Management*, 1 (4), 275–289. doi:10.4467/2450114XJJM.15.019.4828
- Buzzeo, K. and Cifci, F. (2017). Preparing for a career fair. Retrieved from <https://career.fsu.edu/sites/g/files/imported/storage/original/application/1ad1d4dc79aa076c74409d97c046deaf.pdf>.
- Eremie, F. and Jackson, C. (2019). Influence of social cognitive and ethnic variables on academic goals of underrepresented students in science and engineering: A multiple-groups analysis. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 57(2), 205-218

- Eze, M. and Okorafor, D. (2012). Career guidance in secondary schools - A literature review and strategic solutions for Vietnamese rural areas. *American International Journal of Social Science*, 4(5), 135-143
- Gordon, S. (2014). Online career guidance: Does knowledge equate to power for high school students? *Journal of Psychologists and Counsellors in Schools*, 27(2), 190-207. DOI: 10.1017/jgc.2017.7
- Igbozurike, F. Peter, L. and Usman, M. (2018). Strategies for boosting students' enrolment into business education programme of colleges of education. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, 10 (3), 1107~1116
- Igbozurike, D. (2018). Perception of factors that influence students' vocational choice of secretarial studies in tertiary institutions in Edo State of Nigeria. *European Journal of Educational Studies*, 3(2), 325-337
- Igbozurike, F. Ebunu, J. and Onu, D. (2017). *Career guidance services in public senior secondary schools in Kano, Nigeria*. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1238726.pdf>
- Mathe, L.R. and Hapazari, J. (2018). Career guidance in schools, tertiary institutions and workplaces: For the sustainability of nations. *International Journal of Politics and Good Governance*, 9(9.4), 1-17.
- Nwachi, A.I. and Ndimele, S.C. (2021). Perceived influence of selected guidance services on students' career choice in public secondary schools in Rivers State. *International Journal of Innovative Psychology and Social Development*, 9 (2), 75-83
- Ozoemena, S. (2013). Effectiveness of career information collection as a way to promote graduate students' employment. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, 412, 303-308.
- Okoye, H. and Okwelle, G. (2013). *4 benefits of hosting a career fair for high school students*. Retrieved from <https://omella.com/blog/4-benefits-of-hosting-a-career-fair-for-high-school-students>
- Okoye, R. and Arimonu, M.O. (2016). Technical and vocational education in Nigeria: Issues, challenges and a way forward. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(3), 113-118.
- Partha, R. (2020). Career guidance: A way of life. *UGC Care Journal*, 19(39), 22-31.
- Silkes, C., (2010). Hospitality career fairs: Student perceptions of value and usefulness. *Journal of Human Resources in Hospitality and Tourism*, 9(2), 117-130.
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization International Centre for TVET (UNESCO-UNEVOC (2019). *TVET country profile: Nigeria*. Compiled in collaboration with the National Board for Technical Education, Nigeria. Retrieved from: https://unevoc.unesco.org/wtdb/worldtvtdatabase_nga_en.pdf
- Walter, S. M. (2012). *Educational guidance in high schools*. Urbana: The University of Illinois.